

Health Risk Assessment of Heavy Metals via Ingestion and Dermal Absorption of Water in Mogpog and Boac Rivers, Marinduque, Philippines

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Abstract— The purpose of this paper was to assess the potential human health risk posed by heavy metals in surface water in Marinduque, specifically Boac and Mogpog River. Secondary data from Regional Environmental Management Bureau were used. The health risk assessment was patterned from the model made by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA) In this study, the pathways of exposure considered were ingestion, and dermal absorption of water pathways. Result revealed that the mean concentrations of the heavy metals in water varied significantly. Among the two exposure pathways for children, dermal absorption provided a higher Hazard Quotient (HQ) for copper, lead and cadmium. On the contrary, for adults only copper and lead have higher HQ of dermal absorption pathway. Hazard indexes (HI) for adult and children via different exposure pathways were found to be less than the standard value of 1. This means that there is less potential to non-carcinogenic health effects and risks. More so, adults were more at risk to cancer via ingestion of water while for dermal absorption exposure pathway children were more at risk.

Keywords— Dermal Absorption; Hazard Index; Hazard Quotient; Health Risk Assessment; Heavy Metals; Ingestion.

I. INTRODUCTION

World's urban communities are increasing faster than global population as the urbanization progresses (UN-HABITAT, 2004) (Mahmood and Malik, 2014) in the less-developed countries. Though urbanization, to a certain extent, provides economic comfort, it is one of the factors that alter certain environmental condition by increasing waste material build-up through different man-made activities (Mahmood and Malik, 2014).

Two of the most important causes of heavy metal contamination in the environment are mining exploitation and ore smelting. According to Liang et al. in 2017, severe heavy metal contamination is brought about by the huge quantity of wastes produced in mining industries. This heavy metal concentration alters ground and surface waters, agricultural soils and food crops. It even poses great health risk to human population thru different exposure pathways. Environmental pollution arises and becomes one of the biggest concerns of humans today. As time passes by, environmental pollution worsens becoming a major threat to public health on a global scale (Neris et al., 2019).

Heavy metals in waste water drained from tailing ponds pose a serious threat to the environment and to human. Mine tailing wastewater may contain but not limited to different

heavy metals like copper, lead, cadmium and mercury. Mine tailing can percolate in the groundwater sources through seepage. According to Amari et al. (2017) and World Health Organization (WHO) (1993), heavy metals pose a cancer risk to human. The effect of heavy metal contamination occurs in the environment through different exposure methods and pathways (Liang et al., 2017) which includes direct ingestion, skin contact, and inhalation. Lenntech (2004), Dinis and Fuiza (2011) defined heavy metal as elements with high densities. These are also considered toxic even at low concentrations in soil and water sources. These group of elements include cadmium (Cd), copper (Cu), chromium (Cr), iron (Fe), lead, (Pb), silver (Ag) and zinc (Zn) (Farlex, 2005; Duruibe et al., 2007). These metals are the most frequent environmental wastes and the presence in different water sources could be due to either natural or anthropogenic activities. Natural sources may occur because of chemical weathering of minerals and leaching (Titilawo et al., 2018) while mining of ore and smelting of metals are few of the anthropogenic activities by which it can be transferred to the environment.

Groundwater and surface water contamination by heavy metals continues to become a serious threat to the ecological systems in the environment. Although trace concentrations of micro-nutrient heavy metals – Fe, Cu and Zn – an increase concentration still poses toxic effects to the physiology of living organisms (Baby et al., 2010; Nair et al., 2010; Manoj et al., 2012). Meanwhile, Cd and Pb are extremely poisonous even at a low concentration and bioaccumulates in body tissues over long period of time which leads to affect human health negatively (Titilawo et al., 2018).

Since source contamination occurs in different ways, exposure pathways occur differently. According to Neris et al. (2018), there are three pathways by which exposure to heavy metals can occur – soil and sediment; surface and groundwater and particulate matter and vapors (U.S. EPA, 1989). According to Neris et al. in 2018, in industrial set-up humans are continuously subjected to contaminants in the site source and the vulnerability are assessed for contacts to surface soil and water. In most cases, the main exposure pathways are ingestion, dermal contact and inhalation of particulate matter.

More so, adults and children are at higher risk than those in the industrial set-up because the exposure is determined for a lifetime duration (Neris et al., 2018) and that consumption of food is also taken into consideration. In this study, exposure

pathways were adapted and modified from the study of Liang in 2017. These pathways are through ingestion of water, and dermal absorption of water. The concentration of heavy metals (Cd, Cu, and Pb) from water sources were based from the analysis conducted by the Environmental Management Bureau (EMB) from 2012 to 2016.

Oxidation of mine tailings can produce large amounts of acids leading to the mobilization and potential release of metals (Blowes et al., 1991) and posing potential health risks (Tack et al., 1996). Mine tailings are piled up in an open pit or in the tailing ponds. Exposure of sulfide minerals in the tailings to atmospheric oxygen and moisture can result in the formation of acid mine drainage and the release of high concentrations of metals (Forstner and Wittman, 1979; Appelo and Postma, 1996; Stollenwerk, 1994; Herbert, 1996). The chemical speciation of metals is also a good indicator for assessing their potential mobility, availability and toxicity (Bogush and Lazareva, 2011; Gao et al., 2011). The release of metals and their environmental fate and transport are a topic of great concern (Saglam and Akcay, 2016; Kim et al., 2005). The relationship between metals in tailings and the surrounding environment and properties of tailings, soil, and water have also been widely explored (Wang et al., 2013; Candeias et al., 2015)

As described by Linnik (2003), heavy metals pose both mutagenic and carcinogenic effects. The speciation of heavy metals in surface and ground waters significantly affects water quality. Chemical speciation greatly affects the known toxicity and bioavailability of heavy metals (Wittmann, 1993; Linnik and Nabivanets, 1986; Moore and Ramamoorthy, 1987; Pagencopf, 1993; Morrison and Wei, 1991). Free hydrated metal ions are regarded as the most toxic form. The binding of heavy metals in complexes with organic and naturally occurring organic substances more often than not decreases or completely suppresses their toxicity (Luoma, 1983; Flemming and Trevors, 1989). The speciation of heavy metal toxic forms to less active forms decreases the impact of heavy metal pollution and ultimately decreases the health risk. Speciation and degradation of the form of heavy metals depends on the severity of aquatic processes emphasizing the decrease in the concentration of free heavy metal ions. During speciation, complexation of heavy metals with ligands of natural organic is the most valuable process (Linnik, 2003).

Today, heavy metal contamination of water sources has become an important environmental quality issue worldwide most especially in developing countries where there is limited water sanitation and water quality monitoring versus the increased number of population and increased urbanization (Akoro et al., 2008; Ahmad et al., 2010; Ghorade et al., 2014). However, a limited number of health risk assessment have been made (Li et al., 2017; Zhou and Guo, 2015) that focuses on heavy metal contamination in surface and ground waters.

According to Covello and Merkhoher in 2013, risk assessment is an instrument which quantitatively enable to measure uncertainties about the vulnerability - health and environmental consequences - resulting from exposure to certain substances, processes or events. Risk assessment method is a systematic procedure that govern three stages:

hazard identification, risk assessment and risk management (Rodricks and Levy, 2013) which are essential in analyzing and interpreting results. Health risk is the probability of having adverse human effects as a consequence of environmental degradation (Liang, 2017).

Marinduque Island is located 160 km south of Metro Manila and is identified to harbor one of the largest copper reserves in the Philippines (Marges et al., 2011). Mining in the province has its long history since 1969. Although the mining industry in the province have provided a good source of livelihood to many people living there, it has produced so much mine tailings that it has severely polluted surface water of almost the entire province. Two of the severely affected surface water sources are the Boac River and Mogpog River.

The aim of this paper is to assess the potential human health risk as a consequence of heavy metal exposure in surface water in Marinduque, specifically Boac and Mogpog River. This information will enable Marinduqueño implement more consistent policies and actions specifically for those areas where pollution has not reached critical levels yet. This will also provide a concrete basis for the negation and mitigation of heavy metal contamination. The study focused only on the risk exposure through ingestion of water pathway, and dermal absorption of water pathway. Secondary data on the concentration of heavy metals from the Regional Environmental Management Bureau was used.

II. METHODOLOGY

Study Site

The sampling locations were adapted from the water quality monitoring conducted by the Regional Environmental Management Bureau from 2012 to 2016 in Boac and Mogpog River. Six (6) sampling points were identified in the water quality analysis of Boac River and five (5) sampling sites for Mogpog River.

Boac River is classified as Class C under fresh water as per Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) Administrative Order (DAO) No. 2016-08 (Water Quality Guidelines and General Effluent Standards of 2016). The stations were described in Table 1. The corresponding coordinates were obtained by GPS on-site location using Garmin E-Trex portable GPS receiver (REMB, 2016).

TABLE 1. Sampling Sites in Boac River (Boac River Annual Report CY 2016, EMB Regional Office MIMAROPA)

Station Number	Station Identification	Latitude	Longitude
1	Bantay	13° 25' 9.52"	121° 53' 53.10"
2	Balimbing	13° 25' 47.63"	121° 52' 53.28"
3	Sawi	13° 26' 7.08"	121° 51' 15.56"
4	Tampus	13° 26' 48.04"	121° 50' 28.54"
5	Lupac Santol	13° 27' 8.86"	121° 49' 59.03"
6	Tabigue	13° 27' 3.24"	121° 49' 12.13"

Figure 1 shows the map of the ambient water quality monitoring stations of Boac.

Fig. 1. Google Plot of the Ambient Water Quality Monitoring Stations of Boac (Boac River Annual Report CY 2016, EMB Regional Office MIMAROPA)

Mogpog River is classified as Class C under fresh water as per DENR Administrative Order (DAO) No. 2016-08 (Water Quality Guidelines and General Effluent Standards of 2016). The stations were described in Table 2. The corresponding coordinates were obtained by GPS on-site location.

TABLE 2. Sampling Sites in Mogpog River (Mogpog River Annual Report CY 2016, EMB Regional Office MIMAROPA)

Station Number	Station Identification	Latitude	Longitude
1	Bocbob	13° 28' 23.8"	121° 56' 8.11"
2	Manggamnan	13° 28' 58.0"	121° 55' 7.9"
3	Mangyan-Mababad	13° 28' 36.4"	121° 52' 53.2"
4	Sumangga	13° 28' 29.3"	121° 52' 29.9"
5	Nangka II	13° 28' 54.8"	121° 50' 47.7"

Figure 3 shows the map of the ambient water quality monitoring stations of Mogpog.

Fig. 3. Google Plot of the Ambient Water Quality Monitoring Stations of Mogpog (Mogpog River Annual Report CY 2016, EMB Regional Office MIMAROPA)

Sample Collection and Analysis

The concentrations of heavy metal from 2012 to 2016 were obtained from the Ambient Water Quality Analysis conducted

by the Regional Environmental Management Bureau of MIMAROPA Region.

Risk Assessment Methods

In this study, the health risk assessment was patterned from the model made by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA) to evaluate and assess the human health risk as a consequence of heavy metals exposure. The US EPA health risk assessment model has been used by several researchers (Xiao et al., 2017; Chary et al., 2008; Zhou et al., 2016; Mahmood and Malik, 2014). In this study, the pathways of exposure considered were ingestion of water pathway, and dermal absorption of water pathway.

Human Health Risk Assessment

Calculation of Heavy Metal Chronic Daily Intake (CDI)

Copper, cadmium and lead were determined as hazards in the rivers under study. Assessment was conducted to estimate the extent of exposures heavy metal contamination. The extent of exposure was determined by calculating the chronic daily intake dose (CDI, mg/kg/day) (Liang et al., 2017) taken by adults and children (Titilawo et al., 2018). The CDI of the two groups were estimated independently and the exposure was dependent on several factors including level of contamination in the environmental media. The calculation methods of CDI depend across different pathways and were shown on equations 1 and 2. The definition and value of exposure parameter as listed on table 3 (Titilawo et al., 2018; Liang et al., 2017).

$$CDI_{ingestion} = \frac{C \times IR \times ED \times EF \times CF}{BW \times AT} \quad \text{eqn 1}$$

$$CDI_{dermal\ absorption} = \frac{C \times AF \times SA \times ABS \times EF \times ED \times CF}{BW \times AT} \quad \text{eqn 2}$$

Non-Carcinogenic Risks

The possibility of any chronic toxicity was determined thru the hazard quotient (HQ) of the CDI (Titilawo et. al., 2018). HQ is the estimated non-carcinogenic risk threshold value that predicts if an adverse effect may occur. The HQ is calculated using equation 4 shown below.

$$Hazard\ Quotient = CDI \times RFD \quad \text{equation 3}$$

Hazard Index

The over-all Hazard Index (HI) was calculated as the summation of all HQs for the contaminants identified. Several studies (IRIS, 2009; Dinis and Fiuza, 2011; Wei et al., 2015; Yahaya et al., 2017) suggested that if HI is equal to or less than 1.0, no adverse human health effects would be expected to occur but any value above 1.0 means that there is a significant risk level. Kamunda et al. (2016) recommended several levels of risk with respect to HI. When value is below 0.1, the risk is negligible; between 0.1 to 1 as low risk; medium risk if it is between 1 to 4; and high if it exceeds a value of 4. Probability of adverse health effects may occur as the value of HI becomes higher.

TABLE 3. The definition and value of exposure parameters (Titilawo, et al., 2018; Liang et al., 2017)

Parameter	Value of Parameter		Reference
	Adult	Children	
C Heavy metal concentration in water (mg/L)			
IR Ingestion rate of the water being studied (L/day)	2.5	0.78	US EPA (2011)
ED Exposure duration (years)	26	6	US EPA (2011)
EF Frequency of exposure (days/year)	350	350	US EPA (1991)
CF Conversion factor	1 x 10 ⁻⁶	1 x 10 ⁻⁶	US EPA (2004)
BW Average body weight (kg)	80	15	US EPA (2011)
AT Average time (days)	25500	25500	DEA South Africa (2010)
AF Skin adherence factor (mg/cm ²)	0.07	0.2	US EPA (2004)
SA Exposed surface area of skin (cm ²)	19652	6365	US EPA (2011)
ABS Dermal absorption factor	0.1	0.1	US EPA (2011)
SF Carcinogenicity slope factor (mg/kg/day) (Cu)	n/a	n/a	DEA South Africa (2010)
Carcinogenicity slope factor (mg/kg/day) (Pb)	0.0085	0.0085	DEA South Africa (2010)
Carcinogenicity slope factor (mg/kg/day) (Cd)	6.1	6.1	DEA South Africa (2010)
RFD Chronic Oral reference dose (mg/kg/day) (Cu)	4.0 x 10 ⁻²	4.0 x 10 ⁻²	US EPA (2011)
Chronic Oral reference dose (mg/kg/day) (Pb)	3.5 x 10 ⁻³	3.5 x 10 ⁻³	US EPA (2011)
Chronic Oral reference dose (mg/kg/day) (Cd)	1.0 x 10 ⁻³	1.0 x 10 ⁻³	US EPA (2011)
Chronic dermal reference dose (mg/kg/day) (Cu)	1.2 x 10 ⁻²	1.2 x 10 ⁻²	US EPA (2011)
Chronic dermal reference dose (mg/kg/day) (Pb)	5.25 x 10 ⁻⁴	5.25 x 10 ⁻⁴	US EPA (2011)
Chronic dermal reference dose (mg/kg/day) (Cd)	1.0 x 10 ⁻⁵	1.0 x 10 ⁻⁵	US EPA (2011)

Carcinogenic Risks

According to Liang et al. in 2017, the entry of contaminants to human thru different pathways may result to either carcinogenic risk or non-carcinogenic risk. According to Titilawo et. al., 2018, carcinogenic risks estimate the probability of developing cancer upon exposure carcinogenic contaminant over a lifetime. It is calculated by multiplying CDI with cancer slope factor (SF) as shown in equation 4.

$$Cancer\ risk = CDI \times SF \quad \text{equation 4}$$

Cancer risk value is in the acceptable range of 10⁻⁶ to 10⁻⁴. If its value is less than 10⁻⁶, it can be ignored and unacceptable if it exceeds 10⁻⁴.

Equations 1, 2, 3 and 4 were patterned from the studies of Titilawo et al., 2018; Liang et al., 2017.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Concentration of Heavy Metals in Water

Average concentrations of heavy metals in mg/L from 2012 to 2016 for both Boac and Mogpog Rivers are presented in Table 4. These data were collected from the ambient water quality monitoring conducted by EMB. The concentrations were used to calculate the chronic daily intakes for non-carcinogenic and carcinogenic risk assessment.

TABLE 4. Yearly Average Heavy Metal Concentration in Boac and Mogpog River, Marinduque (mg/L)

	BOAC					MOGPOG				
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Copper	0.120	0.009	0.009	0.016	0.009	0.811	1.787	0.205	0.985	0.823
Lead	0.075	0.332	0.256	0.065	0.089	0.062	0.377	0.247	0.116	0.020
Cadmium	0.005	0.009	0.027	0.008	0.004	0.008	0.020	0.081	0.009	0.004

The data presented showed that average concentrations of the heavy metals in water varied significantly. The average ranges were as follows: Cu (0.009 – 1.787 mg/L); Pb (0.020 – 0.332 mg/L); and Cd (0.004 – 0.081 mg/L). It is noted that the Mogpog River’s concentration of copper for the period covered were beyond the allowable 0.00 mg/L limit set by DAO No. 2016-08. For lead concentration, Boac water analysis showed that the average concentration of lead exceeded the standards during the five-year duration. Mogpog water analysis in 2016 is the only period where the concentration does not exceed the water quality guidelines of 0.05 mg/L. For cadmium, in 2014 the concentration exceeded the acceptable limit in Boac while for Mogpog only 2016 analysis did not exceeded the allowable limit of 0.005 mg/L (DAO No. 2016-08).

Health Risk Assessment

Chronic Daily Intake (CDI)

The average daily intake of heavy metals via ingestion of water pathway by adult and children is listed in Tables 5 and 6. These data revealed that there was a fluctuating trend in the daily intake of each heavy metal. For Cu, the highest intake took during 2012 in Boac and 2013 in Mogpog. In 2013, highest Pb intake were recorded for both Boac and Mogpog while for Cd highest intake was noted to happen in 2014 for Boac and Mogpog.

The average daily intake of heavy metals via dermal absorption of water pathway by adult and children is listed in Tables 7 and 8. These data revealed that there was a fluctuating trend in the daily intake of each heavy metal. Boac and Mogpog recorded the highest Cu intake in 2012 and 2013, respectively. In 2013, both Boac and Mogpog had the highest Pb intake. Lastly, Cd has the highest intake during 2014 for Boac and Mogpog. Among the two exposure pathways, dermal absorption accounted for the most of total daily intake for adults and children.

TABLE 5. Yearly Heavy Metal Intake thru Ingestion ($CDI_{\text{Ingestion}}$) for Adults

	BOAC					MOGPOG				
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Copper (10^{-10})	13.4	1.00	1.00	1.76	1.00	90.4	199	22.8	110	91.8
Lead (10^{-10})	8.40	37.0	28.5	7.25	9.25	6.91	42.1	27.6	13.0	2.23
Cadmium (10^{-10})	0.558	1.00	3.03	0.874	0.446	0.848	2.25	8.99	1.00	0.446

TABLE 6. Yearly Heavy Metal Intake thru Ingestion ($CDI_{\text{Ingestion}}$) for Children

	BOAC					MOGPOG				
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Copper (10^{-10})	5.14	0.385	0.385	0.676	0.385	34.7	76.5	8.77	42.2	35.2
Lead (10^{-10})	3.23	14.2	11.0	2.78	3.81	2.66	16.2	10.6	4.99	0.857
Cadmium (10^{-10})	0.214	0.385	1.16	0.336	0.171	0.326	0.865	3.45	0.385	0.171

TABLE 7. Yearly Heavy Metal Intake thru Dermal Absorption (CDI_{dermal}) for Adult

	BOAC					MOGPOG				
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Copper (10^{-10})	736	55.2	55.2	97.0	55.2	4980	10900	1260	6040	5050
Lead (10^{-10})	463	2040	1570	399	546	380	2310	1520	714	123
Cadmium (10^{-10})	30.7	55.2	167	48.0	24.6	46.6	124	495	55.2	24.6

TABLE 8. Yearly Heavy Metal Intake thru Dermal Absorption (CDI_{dermal}) for Children

	BOAC					MOGPOG				
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Copper (10^{-10})	839	62.9	62.9	110	62.9	5670	12500	1430	6880	5750
Lead (10^{-10})	527	2320	1790	454	622	433	2640	1730	814	140
Cadmium (10^{-10})	35.0	62.9	190	54.8	28.0	53.1	141	563	62.9	28.0

Non-Carcinogenic Risks

Hazard Quotient (HQ)

Non carcinogenic risk for adults and children thru different exposure pathways were estimated using the RFD values in Table 3, and CDI values, in Tables 5, 6, 7, and 8. The results were shown in Tables 9, 10, 11, and 12. In risk assessment, if HQs and His exceed the value of 1, probability of potential non-carcinogenic effects may occur while if values are below 1 risk is not observable (USEPA, 2004).

For the adult population, the calculated HQ values for Cu, Pb and Cd were less than one in the two considered pathways. As for children, the calculated HQ values for Cu, Pd and Cd were less than one in all pathways. Among the two exposure pathways for children, dermal absorption provided a higher HQ for copper, lead and cadmium. On the contrary, for adults only copper and lead have higher HQ of dermal absorption pathway.

TABLE 9. Yearly Hazard Quotient for Adult thru Ingestion of Water

	BOAC					MOGPOG				
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Copper (10^{-12})	53.5	4.01	4.01	7.05	4.01	362	797	91.4	439	367
Lead (10^{-12})	2.94	13.0	9.99	2.54	3.47	2.42	14.7	9.66	4.54	0.781
Cadmium (10^{-12})	0.0558	0.100	0.303	0.0874	0.046	0.0848	0.225	0.899	0.100	0.0446

TABLE 10. Yearly Hazard Quotient for Adult thru Dermal Absorption of Water

	BOAC					MOGPOG				
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Copper (10^{-12})	884	66.3	66.3	116	66.3	5970	13200	1510	7250	6060
Lead (10^{-12})	24.3	107	82.4	20.9	28.7	20.0	122	79.7	37.5	6.44
Cadmium (10^{-12})	0.0307	0.0552	0.167	0.0481	0.0245	0.0466	0.124	0.495	0.0552	0.0245

TABLE 11. Yearly Hazard Quotient for Children thru Ingestion of Water

	BOAC					MOGPOG				
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Copper (10^{-12})	20.6	1.54	1.54	2.71	1.54	139	306	35.1	169	141
Lead (10^{-12})	1.13	4.98	3.83	0.974	1.33	0.929	5.66	3.71	1.74	0.300
Cadmium (10^{-12})	0.0214	0.0385	0.116	0.0335	0.0171	0.0325	0.0865	0.345	0.0385	0.0171

TABLE 12. Yearly Hazard Quotient for Children thru Dermal Absorption of Water

	BOAC					MOGPOG				
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Copper (10⁻¹²)	1010	75.5	75.5	133	75.5	6800	15000	1720	8260	6900
Lead (10⁻¹²)	27.6	122	93.9	23.9	32.7	22.7	138	90.8	42.7	7.34
Cadmium (10⁻¹²)	0.0349	0.0629	0.190	0.0547	0.0280	0.0531	0.141	0.563	0.0629	0.0280

Copper is needed by the human body but may cause health problems in high doses (Wuana and Okieimei, 2011). The fate of elemental copper in water is influenced by pH, temperature, hardness, alkalinity, dissolved oxygen and the presence of oxidizing agents and chelating compounds or ions. The cupric form typically is a point of concern in water due to its toxic inorganic species (REMB, 2016, not published).

Researches have shown that lead is a multitarget toxicant, affecting the gastrointestinal tract, cardiovascular system, central and peripheral nervous systems, kidneys, immune system, and reproductive system (RAIS, 2008). Irreversible brain damage has also been reported to occur when Pb level of blood exceeds 100 µg/dl in adults and 80-100 µg/dl in children (RAIS, 2008). Exposure to Pb concentration above RFD causes decreased reaction time, loss of memory, nausea, insomnia, anorexia, and weakness of the joints (NSC, 2009), while the children are believed to be the most prone to toxic effects of Pb, suffering a breakdown of central nervous system (Ogunkunle et al., 2013).

Hazard Index (HI)

The hazard indexes (HI) via ingestion and dermal absorption are shown on Table 13. Hazard indexes for adult

and children via different exposure pathways were found to be less than the standard value of 1. This means that there is no concern for potential non-carcinogenic health effects and risks. The low hazard indexes observed in water sources (Boac and Mogpog Rivers) resulted from the low concentration of the heavy metals in the sample. It can be associated to the natural chemical reactions of the metals to non-organic and organic substances in the environment. The surprisingly low hazard indexes due to heavy metal exposure in water may be attributed to high biological productivity complexation. According to Linnik (2003), in the bodies of water that contains high biological productivity complexation with the participation of natural organic ligands is the dominant factor of stabilization of metals in a solution. This means that complexation makes heavy metals in its bound state – the amount of free ions of metals as the most toxic form are negligible (Linnik, 2003). Complexation allows assessing the potential of natural organic substances in bodies of water to bind to metal ions to form complexes. Hence, possibly decreasing the concentration as ions and lowering the hazard to human.

TABLE 13. Yearly Hazard Index for Adult and Children thru Ingestion and Dermal Absorption of Water

	BOAC					MOGPOG				
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Adult Ingestion (10⁻¹²)	56.50	17.11	14.30	9.68	7.53	364.50	811.93	101.96	443.64	367.83
Children Ingestion (10⁻¹²)	21.75	6.56	5.49	3.72	2.89	139.96	311.75	39.16	170.78	141.32
Adult dermal absorption (10⁻¹²)	908.33	173.36	148.87	136.95	95.02	5990.05	13322.12	1590.20	7287.56	6066.46
Children dermal absorption (10⁻¹²)	1037.63	197.56	169.59	156.95	108.23	6822.75	15138.14	1811.36	8302.76	6907.37

Carcinogenic Risks

The carcinogenic risk values estimated for lead and cadmium were tabulated in Tables 14, 15, 16, and 17 wherein cadmium is the highest contributor. The US EPA considers cancer risk in the range of 1 x 10⁻⁶ to 1 x 10⁻⁴ as acceptable for regulatory purposes (US EPA, 2004). The cancer risks for adults and children thru ingestion of water were found to occur in 2014 at Mogpog River at 5.503 x 10⁻⁹ and 2.119 x 10⁻⁹, respectively of which both were within the acceptable limits.

The cancer risks for adults and children thru dermal absorption of water were found to occur in 2014 at Mogpog River at 3.033 x 10⁻⁷ and 3.415 x 10⁻⁷, respectively of which both were within the acceptable limits. In the current study,

adults were more at risk via ingestion of water while for dermal absorption exposure pathway children were more at risk.

The results presents that dermal absorption is the main contributor to excess lifetime cancer risk. Several studies have linked heavy metal accumulation to numerous health diseases and abnormalities. They cause short- and long-term safety along with environmental and health risk (Njoku et al., 2018). If all other exposure pathways of heavy metals were considered (Adedokun et al., 2016; Jolaoso et al., 2016; Njoku et al., 2016), the potential health risks for residents (Njoku et al., 2018) surrounding Boac and Mogpog rivers might actually be higher.

TABLE 14. Yearly Heavy Metal Cancer Risk Assessment for Adult thru Ingestion of Water

	BOAC					MOGPOG				
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Lead (10⁻¹²)	7.14	31.5	24.3	6.16	8.44	5.88	35.8	23.5	11.0	1.90
Cadmium (10⁻¹²)	340	612	1850	533	272	517	1370	5480	612	272
TOTAL (10⁻¹²)	347.14	643.5	1874.3	539.16	280.44	522.88	1405.8	5503.5	623	273.9

TABLE 15. Yearly Heavy Metal Cancer Risk Assessment for Children thru Ingestion of Water

	BOAC					MOGPOG				
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Lead (10⁻¹²)	2.74	12.1	9.31	2.37	3.24	2.26	13.7	9.01	4.24	0.728
Cadmium (10⁻¹²)	131	0.328	0.989	0.285	0.146	199	528	2110	235	104
TOTAL (10⁻¹²)	133.74	12.428	10.299	2.655	3.386	201.26	541.7	2119.01	239.24	104.728

TABLE 16. Yearly Heavy Metal Cancer Risk Assessment for Adult thru Dermal Absorption of Water

	BOAC					MOGPOG				
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Lead (10⁻¹²)	393	1730	1330	339	464	323	1970	1290	607	104
Cadmium (10⁻¹²)	18700	33700	102000	29300	15000	28400	75600	302000	33700	15000
TOTAL (10⁻¹²)	19093	35430	103330	29639	15464	28723	77570	303290	34307	15104

TABLE 17. Yearly Heavy Metal Cancer Risk Assessment for Children thru Dermal Absorption of Water

	BOAC					MOGPOG				
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Lead (10⁻¹²)	448	1970	1520	386	529	368	2240	1470	691	119
Cadmium (10⁻¹²)	21300	53.5	161	46.5	23.8	32400	86100	340000	38400	17100
TOTAL (10⁻¹²)	21748	2023.5	1681	432.5	552.8	32768	88340	341470	39091	17219

IV. CONCLUSION

As shown in this study, dermal absorption exposure pathway is the greatest contributor to non-carcinogenic risk. For carcinogenic effects, dermal absorption exposure pathway contributes the most to cancer risk. Based on the results from the present study, it can be generalized that the Marcopper tragedy contributes to the elevated heavy metal concentration in the surrounding Boac and Mogpog rivers. Although the hazard quotient (HQ), hazard index (HI) and cancer risks are in the allowable limits, it is still necessary to make precautionary measures avoiding dermal absorption exposure pathway since it posed the highest contribution to both non-carcinogenic and carcinogenic risks.

Based from the results, non-carcinogenic effect of exposure to toxic metals in both rivers is less likely to occur. It is highly evident that the carcinogenic effect can be experience with constant exposure to the water of Mogpog River. More so, children living in the surroundings of Mogpog River have higher probability of being exposed to risk if continued usage and exposure to untreated water is made.

The present study provides a good basis for further research on the human health risk in other areas surrounding the source of heavy metal contaminants. It is highly recommended regular water quality analysis be sustained to ensure that non-carcinogenic and carcinogenic risks are monitored. A more in depth analysis should be done to trace the cause of the fluctuating levels of heavy metals especially cadmium and lead. In order to reduce the heavy metal concentrations in the waters of Boac and Mogpog rivers, planting plants with high absorptive capacity for heavy metals must be conducted.

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